

Data Output Olah SmartPLS

Correlations

		z1_1	z1_2	z1_3	z1_4	z1_5	z1_6	z1_total
z1_1	Pearson Correlation	1	.212*	.277**	.550**	.073	.343**	.600**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.023	.003	.000	.437	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
z1_2	Pearson Correlation	.212*	1	.444**	.272**	.357**	.286**	.650**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.023		.000	.003	.000	.002	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
z1_3	Pearson Correlation	.277**	.444**	1	.433**	.421**	.344**	.709**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
z1_4	Pearson Correlation	.550**	.272**	.433**	1	.317**	.575**	.781**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.003	.000		.001	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
z1_5	Pearson Correlation	.073	.357**	.421**	.317**	1	.370**	.614**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.437	.000	.000	.001		.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
z1_6	Pearson Correlation	.343**	.286**	.344**	.575**	.370**	1	.712**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.002	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
z1_total	Pearson Correlation	.600**	.650**	.709**	.781**	.614**	.712**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

		x1	x2	x3	x4	x5	x6	x_total
x1	Pearson Correlation	1	.533**	.563**	.601**	.674**	.627**	.788**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
x2	Pearson Correlation	.533**	1	.572**	.665**	.582**	.682**	.792**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
x3	Pearson Correlation	.563**	.572**	1	.674**	.733**	.669**	.844**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
x4	Pearson Correlation	.601**	.665**	.674**	1	.742**	.714**	.872**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
x5	Pearson Correlation	.674**	.582**	.733**	.742**	1	.723**	.884**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
x6	Pearson Correlation	.627**	.682**	.669**	.714**	.723**	1	.867**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115
x_total	Pearson Correlation	.788**	.792**	.844**	.872**	.884**	.867**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

		z2_1	z2_2	z2_3	z2_4	z2_total
z2_1	Pearson Correlation	1	.527**	.549**	.496**	.786**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115
z2_2	Pearson Correlation	.527**	1	.588**	.629**	.840**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115
z2_3	Pearson Correlation	.549**	.588**	1	.552**	.825**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115
z2_4	Pearson Correlation	.496**	.629**	.552**	1	.817**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115
z2_total	Pearson Correlation	.786**	.840**	.825**	.817**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	115	115	115	115	115

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

		z3_1	z3_2	z3_3	z3_4	z3_5	z3_total
z3_1	Pearson Correlation	1	.367**	.525**	.561**	.557**	.759**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
z3_2	Pearson Correlation	.367**	1	.647**	.684**	.468**	.783**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
z3_3	Pearson Correlation	.525**	.647**	1	.706**	.553**	.854**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
z3_4	Pearson Correlation	.561**	.684**	.706**	1	.522**	.862**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
z3_5	Pearson Correlation	.557**	.468**	.553**	.522**	1	.765**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
z3_total	Pearson Correlation	.759**	.783**	.854**	.862**	.765**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlations

		y1	y2	y3	y4	y5	y_total
y1	Pearson Correlation	1	.098	-.145	-.082	-.009	.356**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.295	.123	.381	.927	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
y2	Pearson Correlation	.098	1	.215*	.289**	-.105	.590**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.295		.021	.002	.264	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
y3	Pearson Correlation	-.145	.215*	1	.251**	.242**	.589**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.123	.021		.007	.009	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
y4	Pearson Correlation	-.082	.289**	.251**	1	.068	.616**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.381	.002	.007		.471	.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
y5	Pearson Correlation	-.009	-.105	.242**	.068	1	.424**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.927	.264	.009	.471		.000
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115
y_total	Pearson Correlation	.356**	.590**	.589**	.616**	.424**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	115	115	115	115	115	115

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

X

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.9165	6

Z1

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.764	6

Z2

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.834	4

Z3

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.862	5

Y

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.706	5

Multiko

Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)		
z1_total	.968	1.033
z2_total	.931	1.074
z3_total	.973	1.028
x_tot	.928	1.078

a. Dependent Variable: y_total

Normalitas

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Unstandardized Residual
N	115
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.064 ^c

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Hetero

Coefficients^a

Model	Sig.		
1 (Constant)	.001		
z1_total	.994		
z2_total	.085		
z3_total	.073		
x_tot	.099		

a. Dependent Variable: abs_res

Auto korelasi

Model Summary^b

Model	Durbin-Watson
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1	2.164
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a. Predictors: (Constant), z3_total, x_total, z1_total, z2_total

b. Dependent Variable: y_total

Mra

x-y

Model Summary^b

Model	R Square
1	.583

a. Predictors: (Constant), z1_total

b. Dependent Variable: y_total

Coefficients^a

Model		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.620	
	z1_total	14.914	.000

a. Dependent Variable: y_total

M1-y

Model Summary^b

Model	R Square
1	.21

a. Predictors: (Constant), z1_total

b. Dependent Variable: y_total

Coefficients^a

Model		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.620	
	z1_total	25.171	.000

a. Dependent Variable: y_total

M2-y

Model Summary^b

Model	R Square
1	.32

a. Predictors: (Constant), z2_total

b. Dependent Variable: y_total

Coefficients^a

Model		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.578	
	z2_total	11.234	.000

a. Dependent Variable: y_total

M3-y

Model Summary^b

Model	R Square
1	.232

a. Predictors: (Constant), z3_total

b. Dependent Variable: y_total

Coefficients^a

Model		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.539	
	z3_total	20.450	.000

a. Dependent Variable: y_total

x-m1-y

Model Summary^b

Model	R Square
1	.21

a. Predictors: (Constant), x_m1, x_total

b. Dependent Variable: y_total

Coefficients^a

Model		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.308	
	x_m1	28.253	.000

a. Dependent Variable: y_total

x-m2-y

Model Summary^b

Model	R Square
1	.23

a. Predictors: (Constant), x_m2, x_total

b. Dependent Variable: y_total

Coefficients^a

Model		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.377	
	x_m2	28.102	.000

a. Dependent Variable: y_total

x-m3-y

Model Summary^b

Model	R Square
1	.055

a. Predictors: (Constant), x_m3, x_total

b. Dependent Variable: y_total

Coefficients^a

Model		t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.401	
	x m3	29.021	.018.000